

Chromium(III) complexes of asparagine – Preparation and exploration of its viability as supplement for chromium deficiency

Anita Kr. Gupta^{*a}, Manju Kumari^b and H. O. Pandey^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, S. S. M. College, Ranchi-834 008, Jharkhand, India

E-mail : guptaanitak@yahoo.in

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Nirmala College, Ranchi-834 002, Jharkhand, India

E-mail : manjupandeya@gmail.com

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Ranchi University, Ranchi-834 008, Jharkhand, India

E-mail : hpandey62@yahoo.com

Manuscript received online 23 May 2014, accepted 08 July 2014

Abstract : Chromium(III) is biologically active ingredient found in food and known to enhance the efficiency of insulin which in turn controls the blood sugar and depression in natural health. Chromium deficiency is rare and can be improved by taking it from different sources of food or commercially available supplements such as chromium picolinate and chromium polynicotinate. In the present paper, we report the preparation and characterization of products formed by the interaction of chromium(VI) as oxidant with asparagine and explore their viability as chromium supplement.

Keywords : Asparagine, ditertiary butyl chromate, microwave, chromium deficiency.

Introduction

Asparagine has the credit of being the first amino acid to be isolated. It was isolated from asparagus in 1806 by French chemist Louis Nicolas Vauquelin and Pierre Jean Robiquet¹. It is a non-essential amino acid which may be enzymatically synthesized in the body from the precursor oxaloacetate.

On the other hand, chromium(III) is known to enhance the action of insulin, a hormone critical to metabolism and storage of carbohydrate, fat and protein in body². Diets rich in sugar can increase chromium excretion in the urine³. Infection, acute exercise, pregnancy lactation and stressful status increase chromium losses and can lead to deficiency⁴. This deficiency can be made up by taking it from food source, but most of the food provide only small amount (less than 2 microgram) of chromium. Few supplements to cure chromium deficiency available in the market are chromium picolinate, chromium polynicotinate⁵, etc.

In the present work, we have taken asparagine as or-

ganic substrate in water as solvent and treated it with ditertiary butyl chromate in order to prepare some variant of chromium(III) which can function as supplement for chromium deficiency. Ditertiary butyl chromate⁶ is one of the best option as chromium(VI)-based oxidants among the large number of variants available like dipyridine chromium(VI) oxide⁷, chromium trioxide 3,5-dimethyl pyrozole complex⁸, pyridinium fluoro chromate⁹, benzylmethylammonium fluorochromate¹⁰, etc. due to its docility, versatility and efficiency. A large number of papers have come up dealing with the oxidation of organic substrates by ditertiary butyl chromate^{11,12} under ordinary stirring and heating conditions. However, the increasing use of microwave as energy source has prompted not only its application in the organic synthetic work but the revision of the old methods too. This is in accordance with the principles of clean and green chemistry¹³. The preparation of asparagine variant of chromium(III) as reported in the paper is a part of project undertaken by the authors with the caption “*preparation*

and characterization of complexes of chromium with biologically active organic ligands”, under which a large number of products of amino acids and carbohydrates have been prepared¹⁴ by microwave irradiation.

Material and methods :

The chemicals were all A.R. grade. Freshly prepared solutions were used. The experimental method used in the present work consists of mainly

(i) *Preparation of ditertiary butyl chromate :* The oxidant was prepared by dissolving accurately weighed amount of dry and powdered chromium trioxide in calculated volume of tertiary butyl alcohol at room temperature. Care was taken to avoid bigger pieces of CrO_3 as this may cause explosive reaction leading to fire.

(ii) *Preparation of solution of asparagine :* Accurately weighted amounts of pure asparagine required for a particular substrate : oxidant molar ratio were dissolved in 50 ml of water. The substrate : oxidant molar ratio which led to positive results were 1 : 2, 2 : 3, 1 : 1, 2 : 1 and 3 : 1. For 1 : 2 molar ratio, the weight of asparagine and CrO_3 were 1.5 g and 2 g, respectively. Similarly, other solutions were made with the calculated quantity of asparagine and chromium trioxide.

(iii) *Reaction between asparagine solution and oxidant :* The two solutions as prepared in (i) and (ii) were mixed carefully and stirred on a mechanical stirrer for several minutes before subjecting it to microwave irradiation. The wattage, period of irradiating and standing for different substrate : oxidant ratios are tabulated in Table 1. The solid products of different colours and compositions were obtained which were washed several times

with acetone to remove any impurities and collected in air tight bottles as samples AS-12, AS-23, AS-11, AS-21 and AS-31.

(iv) *Characterization of the products :* The products were characterized by elemental analysis by “Elemental analyser - Heraeus Vario EL III Carlo Erba 1108”, FTIR curves obtained by “Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer - Shimadzu 8201 PC” and DTA-TGA thermogravimetric mass loss pattern. The solubility of the products in different solvents was also tested.

Results and discussion

The reaction conditions in Table 1 show that the formation of compounds/complexes of chromium with asparagine is very difficult. The same is observed in cases of other amino acids too, as explored by the authors of this paper¹⁴ and others¹⁵. However, enzymatically asparagine is oxidised to asparatic acid in presence of asparaginase and then into oxaloacetic acid which is an important member of citric acid cycle. Asparagine is also a precursor to acrylamide when carbohydrate containing food stuff is fried in presence of reducing sugar^{16,17}. The chemical oxidation of asparagine under microwave condition leads to different products including nitro derivatives, also as mentioned in Table 2. The degradative oxidation of the substrate takes place when the ratio of oxidant is more as substantiated by the presence of smaller fragments in case of AS-12 and AS-23. The formation of ammonia in higher ratio of oxidant is supported by its presence in AS-12 and AS-23 as ligand¹⁵. This is not observed in other cases where the extent of oxidation is less. The extent of degradative oxidation increases as the

Table 1. Reaction conditions

Sample code	Solvent	S : O ratio	Stirring (min)	Irradiation	Left (Days)
AS-12	Water	1 : 2	10	1 min (180 w) + 4 min (450 w)	42
AS-23	Water	2 : 3	15	4 min (450 w)	42
AS-11	Water	1 : 1	50	2 min (180 w) + 3 min (270 w) + 10 min (360 w) + 10 min (450 w)	45
AS-21	Water	2 : 1	57	3 min (180 w) + 2 min (270 w) + 8 min (360 w) + 6 min (450 w)	30
AS-31	Water	3 : 1	70	5 min (270 w) + 20 min (360 w) + 4 min (450 w) + 4 min (540 w)	45

Table 2. Product characterisation

Sample code	Colour	Solubility in water	Empirical formula	Formulation
AS-12	Deep brown	Partially soluble	$C_{10}H_{27}O_{30}N_4Cr_2$	$Cr_2O_3 \cdot 3HOOC \cdot CH \cdot NO_2 \cdot COOH \cdot HCOOH \cdot NH_3 \cdot 7H_2O$ ($C_{10}H_{28}O_{30}N_4Cr_2$)
AS-23	Brown	Partially soluble	$C_{10}H_{28}O_{26}N_4Cr_2$	$Cr_2O_3 \cdot HOOCCH_2CH \cdot NH_2 \cdot COOH \cdot 2(COOH \cdot CH \cdot NO_2 \cdot COOH) \cdot NH_3 \cdot 7H_2O$ ($C_{10}H_{30}O_{26}N_4Cr_2$)
AS-11	Brown	Soluble	$C_6H_{16}O_{11}N_3Cr$	$CrO_2 \cdot H_2N \cdot CO \cdot CH_2 \cdot CH \cdot NH_2 \cdot COOH \cdot NO_2 \cdot CH_2 \cdot COOH \cdot 2H_2O$ ($C_6H_{15}O_{11}N_3Cr$)
AS-21	Light brown	Soluble	$C_{11}H_{26}O_{14}N_5Cr$	$CrO_2 \cdot 2H_2NCOCH_2CHNH_2 \cdot COOH \cdot CH_3 \cdot CH \cdot NO_2 \cdot COOH \cdot 2H_2O$ ($C_{11}H_{25}O_{14}N_5Cr$)
AS-31	Mustard yellow	Soluble	$C_{13}H_{37}O_{15}N_6Cr$	$CrO \cdot 2H_2NCOCH_2CHNH_2 \cdot COOH \cdot COOH \cdot CHNH_2 \cdot COOH \cdot NH_2 \cdot CH_2 \cdot COOH \cdot 2H_2O$ ($C_{13}H_{30}O_{15}N_6Cr$)

proportion of oxidant is raised. This is also supported by the observation that unoxidised asparagine is associated with AS-11, AS-21 and AS-31 whereas highly oxidised fragment HCOOH is present in AS-12 where the ratio of oxidant is more. Again, the solubility of the products in water is more in those cases when asparagine itself is present as ligands. The number of water molecules in the products AS-12 and AS-23 is more whereas it is less in products AS-11, AS-21 and AS-31. This may be due to the fact that greater extent of oxidation leads to the formation of smaller organic moiety and greater number of water molecules.

The strikingly different colour of AS-31 along with its greater solubility in water and presence of only amino acids and water as ligands makes it much different from other products. The presence of amino acids in the form of ion is not a remote possibility and thus the assumption that one carboxylic group is present as carboxylate ion supports the presence of chromium in plus three state in the sample. On the basis of above facts, we can very well consider that AS-31 is a potential food supplement for chromium deficiency if it clears the sorption¹⁸ and other biological tests.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to CIF, BIT, Mesra for providing FTIR and DTA-TGA data of the samples.

References

1. L. N. Vauquelin and P. J. Robiquet, *Annales de Chimie*, 1806, **57**, 88.
2. R. Anderson, N. Cheng, N. Bryden, M. P. Marilyn, C. Nanping, C. Jiaming and F. Jinduang, *Diabetes*, 1997, **46**, 1786.
3. A. S. Kozlovsky, P. B. Moser, S. Reiser and R. A. Anderson, *Metabolism*, 1986, **35**, 515.
4. R. Anderson, "Stress Effects on Chromium Nutrition in Human and Animals", 10th ed., Nottingham University Press, England, 1994.
5. H. G. Preuss, B. Echard, N. V. Perricone, D. Bagchi, T. Yasmin and S. J. Stohs, *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry*, 2008, **102**, 1986.
6. R. V. Oppenauer and H. Oberrauch, *Anales Assoc. Quim-Argentina*, 1949, **37**, 246.
7. J. C. Collins, W. W. Hess and F. J. Frank, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1968, **9**, 3363.
8. E. J. Corey and G. W. J. Fleet, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1973, 4499.
9. M. N. Bhattacharjee, M. K. Chaudhury, H. S. Dasgupta and N. Roy, *Synthesis*, 1982, 588.
10. M. Z. Kassaea, G. H. Sajjadi and A. S. Z. Sayeed, *Pittcon*, March 9-14, 2003, Orlando, Florida, Abstracts 1200-7P.
11. A. K. Gupta and H. O. Pandey, *Asian J. Exp. Sci.*, 2012, **26**, 43.
12. A. K. Gupta, Manju Kumari and H. O. Pandey, *J. Chemtracks*, 2011, **13**, 219.
13. P. Lidstrom, J. Tierney, B. Wathe and J. Westman, *Tetrahedron Report No. 589*, 2001, **57**, 9225.
14. A. K. Gupta and H. O. Pandey, *Chemical Science Transaction*, 2014, **3**, in press (821).

15. Neeraj, H. O. Pandey and G. D. Mishra, *J. Chemtracks*, 2009, **11**, 481.
16. F. J. Hidalgo, R. M. Delgado, J. L. Navarro and R. Zamora, *Journal of Agriculture and Food Chemistry*, 2010, **58**, 10512.
17. D. Zyzak, *Cincinnati*, Ohio, Press Release, 2002.
18. Z. Luo, A. Wadhwan and E. J. Bouwer, *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Tech.*, 2010, **7**, 1.